

Cultivating Digital Storytelling Translation Competence in Foreign Language Majors via Chinese Narrative Integration

Yan Zhang

School of International Education, Jilin Engineering Normal University, Changchun, Jilin, China

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ABSTRACT

In the contemporary era, foreign language education plays a vital role in "telling China story well," enabling global audiences to understand China and amplifying China's voice internationally. Despite its growing significance, current practices in foreign language teaching aimed at this goal remain exploratory, facing challenges such as limited ideological and political resources, insufficient teacher competencies in integrating ideology, and a lack of an engaging storytelling environment. Translation courses for foreign language majors, with their rich disciplinary features, offer significant potential for embedding ideological and political education. This study investigates an innovative approach to cultivating translation abilities by integrating digital storytelling within these courses. By expanding the traditional "language-centered" paradigm of translation instruction, the research explores how digital storytelling can enhance both translation competence and ideological engagement. The findings aim to provide practical strategies and theoretical insights for the ideological and political construction of translation courses, ultimately contributing to more effective foreign language education aligned with the mission of sharing China's stories globally.

KEYWORDS

Digital storytelling, Translation education, Foreign language teaching, Ideological and political education, China story

1. Introduction

In the new era, foreign language education shoulders the new missions of "Telling China story well", making the world understand China, and spreading China's voice globally [1]. "Telling China story well" deepens the connotation and significance of foreign language teaching. However, current foreign language teaching practices focused on "telling China story well" are still in the exploratory stage. Issues such as the scarcity of ideological and political materials, teachers' lack of ideological and political teaching competencies, and the lack of a strong storytelling atmosphere [2] highlight the necessity of strengthening the ideological and political construction of foreign language courses centered on "telling China story well." Among the numerous foreign language courses, translation courses for foreign language majors contain rich disciplinary characteristics and have high potential for integrating ideological and political education [3]. The mode of ideological and political construction within translation courses for foreign language majors deserves in-depth exploration. This study aims to expand the

traditional "languagecentered" translation teaching concept and explore an innovative path for cultivating translation abilities based on digital storytelling, hoping to provide reference and inspiration for the ideological and political construction of translation courses for foreign language majors.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Integrating China Story into Foreign Language Education

Foreign language majors in universities possess unique advantages in language skills, enabling them to bridge friendly communication between China and other countries in ways that resonate with overseas readers [4]. Research on integrating the "China Story" into foreign language education began with Xu [5]. Current research themes in "China Story" within college English courses include the following:

- 1) Theoretical discussions, such as Kajder et al. exploring strategies for constructing digital stories as a means of effective storytelling [6];
- 2) Research on teaching activities, such as Meadows supporting students' participation in digital storytelling through research-based practices in new media [7];
- 3) Teaching status surveys, such as Shiju examining the role of national language capacity in global competition, offering new perspectives on expressing Chinese culture [8].

2.2. Digital Storytelling

The definition of digital storytelling is continuously evolving. It can be understood as "short media stories combining voice, images, and music" [9], as presenting stories on a screen via short videos [10], or as short media stories created using nonlinear tools and computers [11]. In recent years, digital storytelling has been increasingly integrated into teaching, emphasizing students as the primary creators in classroom settings. They use multimedia tools to create videos, incorporating elements like images, animations, videos, and audio to tell 3-5-minute stories. Clearly, digital storytelling is a teaching method that integrates digital, media, and discipline knowledge [12]. It primarily employs voice, images, videos, text, music, and other elements to comprehensively convey stories related to disciplinary content, making it a multifunctional and powerful learning approach.

In summary, research on integrating China Story into foreign language education has emerged and is growing vigorously. The research outcomes cover a wide range of content and perspectives. However, there are three main shortcomings: First, research on integrating China Story into foreign language education focuses on speech, oral communication, or intercultural communication courses, lacking attention to input and output in translation courses [13]. Second, the narrative form is singular, and stories are predominantly told in text-based languages, with less use of other digital narrative forms such as images, videos, and hypertexts. In view of this, this study intends to discuss the "new narration" of China Story using digital storytelling based on translation courses, innovate the translation ability cultivation of foreign language majors, and help them become practitioners and spreaders of "telling China story well."

3. Cultivation Path for Digital Storytelling Translation Abilities of Foreign Language Majors

This study aims to cultivate foreign language learners who possess patriotism and a global perspective, can spread China's voice, have firm stances, are rational and thoughtful, possess cultural awareness and analytical skills, and

can accurately translate between Chinese and English. This cultivation path encompasses "two foundations," "three kinds of awareness," and "three strategies."

"Two foundations" include relying on disciplinary characteristics and relying on digital storytelling. Relying on disciplinary characteristics means students must rely on translation discipline theoretical knowledge to fully interpret translation content, select translation strategies, engage in translation practice, etc. Relying on digital storytelling means utilizing digital storytelling techniques in translation to enhance the dissemination effectiveness of China Story [14].

"Three kinds of awareness" include analytical awareness, dimensional awareness, and developmental awareness. Analytical awareness refers to fostering students' analytical ability regarding the translation subject, content, target audience, channels, and effects during China Story translation training. Dimensional awareness means translation content includes comparisons of civilizations, cultures, and social statuses, deepening understanding of contemporary China and the world through civilization comparisons, dialogues, and mutual learning. Developmental awareness means giving translation content a developmental perspective, enabling it to review history to observe the present and look forward to the future.

Based on "two foundations" and "three kinds of awareness," practices are implemented through three strategies: image narration, audiovisual narration, and hypertext narration. Among them, image narration refers to using images as an information medium to effectively convey the essence and meaning of events to readers through storytelling. Audiovisual narration means rewriting paper texts into audiovisual works such as films and dramas, transforming flat and static narration into three-dimensional and dynamic narration. Hypertext narration refers to the process of rewriting paper texts into hypertexts such as webpages, essentially a rewriting of the original text. Regarding evaluation methods, the primary methods are diversified evaluation, process-oriented evaluation, and value-added evaluation. Diversified evaluation is manifested in the diversification of evaluation subjects and objects. Process-oriented evaluation is reflected in comprehensive evaluation across teaching steps and interactive improvement of teaching evaluations. Value-added evaluation means not solely measuring learning effectiveness based on the development and changes in translation abilities but also considering related ideological and political competencies, learning engagement, and growth in course satisfaction.

4. Conclusion

This study constructs a cultivation path for digital storytelling translation abilities of foreign language majors based on "telling China story well." Through the "three-in-one" cultivation objective, the cultivation path with "two foundations, three kinds of awareness, and three strategies," as well as diversified, process-oriented, and value-added evaluation methods, it deeply explores the ideological and political elements within translation courses, fulfilling the high integration of value shaping, knowledge imparting, and ability cultivation. The teaching objectives, content, and student enrollment of core courses for foreign language majors vary. Future research can further explore digital storytelling translation ability cultivation paths suitable for different courses within foreign language majors based on the existing path.

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